

Epidemiological data of Coxsackie and Echo viruses in N. Greece

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Summary

The circulation of Coxsackie and Echo viruses is investigated in a period of fourteen years. Clinical data were reported and IgM and IgG specific antibodies were detected by ELISA and IFA techniques for 6654 specimens (5368 for Coxsackie, 1286 for Echo) collected in hospitals of N. Greece. The results revealed 653 IgM positive and 2234 IgG positive specimens for Coxsackie as well as 98 IgM positive and 189 IgG positive specimens for Echo viruses. Coxsackie and Echo infections affected both genders and a statistically significant increase of IgM Coxsackie antibodies in females was found. Regarding the Coxsackie infections, 34.6% happened in spring, while Echo infections happened mainly in autumn and winter (62.2%). The infection rate generally decreased with age except for Echo viruses that infected the 19-60y individuals more than the 0-6y ones. Coxsackie viruses most often caused respiratory illness (IgM 19.9%) pre-

senting statistically significant difference from the rest of clinical manifestations, while Echo mostly caused gastroenteritis (20.4%) though without total statistical significance. No statistically significant difference was observed for clinical manifestations between males and females.

Key words

Coxsackie, ECHO, enteroviruses, N. Greece, epidemiology

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Introduction

Human enteroviruses are an RNA-virus group belonging to the family Picornaviridae and cause plenty of clinical syndromes worldwide; the wide spectrum of diseases caused by the non-polio viruses (group A and B coxsackieviruses, echoviruses) appear in people of all ages.^{1,2,3} Knowledge about these viruses is being accumulated for decades. Sporadic acute gastroenteritis has a major impact on morbidity caused by a variety of enteroviral species,⁴ while lymphocytosis, splenohepatomegaly may be caused by Coxsackie A, B as well as Echo viruses, often accompanied by various other symptoms as well.^{5,6} Fever and sore throat may also appear, often followed by painful vesicular eruptions of the oral mucosa.^{7,8} Coxsackie B and Echo have been proved accountable for 90% of cases of aseptic meningitis in patients younger than one year and 50% of cases in older children and adults,^{9,10,11} while echoviruses have been found to cause encephalitis as well.¹² Enteroviruses, mostly Coxsackie B, have been confirmed as common causes of myopericarditis.¹³ Though enteroviral myopericarditis may generally affect children and adults, it may present high rates of mortality among neonatal children.^{14,2} Coxsackie A viruses are the most common cause of hand, foot and mouth disease and other cutaneous rashes, most commonly in children,¹⁵ sometimes complicated by neurological manifestations.³ Coxsackie B has been recognized as a common cause for nonspecific respiratory tract infections or epidemic pleurodynia.^{16,17,18}

Enteroviruses have been also detected be detected in children with atypical febrile illness during summer-autumn periods.¹⁹ Enteroviral infections may have similarities to non-enteroviral ones concerning onset, presentation signs and total duration of illness (>7 days in both cases).^{20,19,6}

A great number of epidemiological studies conducted since the second half of the 20th century suggest that enteroviral infections form a seasonal pattern and the incidence is higher in the summer and autumn in temperate climates, while there is while no seasonal pattern has been observed in tropical climates. Enteroviral infections affect all age groups but mainly in children below 1 year of age. Seventy percent of the enteroviral infections reported to the WHO refer to children below the age of 10 year.²¹

In Europe, epidemiological peaks have been observed every few years without any obvious standard seasonal pattern.^{22,18,23,24,21} Due to the lack of vast epidemiological approach in Greece, it was considered as important to assess the recent infection status, the proportions of immune population as well as the distribution of the non-polio enteroviral infections.

The main objectives of this study are:

1. recognition of current infections by Coxsackie and Echo viruses in the region;
2. revealing the proportions of immune population;
3. seasonal, age and gender distribution of the infections;
4. correlation with clinical syndromes.

Methods

The material for the present study originated as archive data of the 2nd Department of Microbiology, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, referring to the period 2003-2016. Specific IgM and IgG antibodies were detected by immunofluorescence (IFA, Bios GmbH Labordiagnostik, Germany) and/or immunoenzymatic (ELISA, Virion/Serion GmbH, Germany) techniques in serum samples collected in hospitals of northern Greece. A total of 6654 clinical samples were studied, 5368 for Coxsackie and 1286 for Echo. Statistical analysis was conducted with SPSS v.23.

Results

IgM specific antibodies against Coxsackie viruses were detected in 653 samples and IgG in 2234 ones, while

IgM specific antibodies against Echo viruses were detected in 98 and IgG in 189 samples.

Age

Positive patients were divided into four age groups, 0-6y, 7-18y, 19-60y and >60y; Coxsackie specific and Echo specific IgM and IgG antibodies were detected in each age group as reported on Table 1.

The percentages for every IgM(+) and IgG(+) age group over the total number of IgM(+) and IgG(+) samples respectively present the distribution of acute infections and immunity throughout the age groups as shown in Figures 1 and 2. The numbers of positives generally decreased with age for both Coxsackie and Echo except for the 19-60y group where the decrease pattern was not always followed.

All age groups were compared statistically to each other for each antibody category. For Coxsackie IgM(+) p varied from 0.0000 to 0.0006; for IgG(+) p=0.0000 except when comparing groups 7-18y to 19-60y where

Table 1 Age distribution for Coxsackie and Echo viruses

Age group	Tested for Coxsackie	Coxsackie IgM	Coxsackie IgG	Tested for Echo	Echo IgM	Echo IgG
0-6	2113	303	856	454	43	66
7-18	1158	177	610	271	13	58
19-60	1526	125	656	395	35	55
>60	571	48	112	166	7	10
Total	5368	653	2234	1286	98	189

Figure 1 Percentages calculated for every IgM(+) age group over the total of IgM(+) samples (N=653)

Figure 2 Percentages calculated for every IgG(+) age group over the total of IgG(+) samples (N=2234)

Table 2 Gender distribution of Coxsackie and ECHO infections

	Coxsackie		ECHO	
	IgM (+)	IgG (+)	IgM (+)	IgG (+)
Male	296 45.3%	1186 53.1%	52 53.1%	106 56.1%
Female	357 54.7%	1048 46.9%	46 46.9%	83 43.9%
Total	653	2234	98	189

Figure 3 Seasonal distribution of Coxsackie and Echo infections

no statistically significant difference was noted ($p=0.1267$). For Echo IgM(+) p varied from 0.0000 to 0.0003 except when comparing groups 0-6y to 19-60y and groups 7-18y to >60y where no statistically significant difference was noted ($p=0.2430$ and 0.1568 respectively). Statistically significant differences were revealed for Echo IgG ($p=0.0000$) when comparing groups 0-6y to >60y, 7-18y to >60y and 19-60y to >60y; on the contrary, comparing the groups 0-6y to 7-18y and 0-6y to 19-60y $p=0.3808$ and 0.2252 respectively. Furthermore children (0-18y) were also compared statistically with adults in total (>19y), and a statistical difference was found for both Coxsackie IgM(+) and IgG(+) ($p=0.0000$), as well as for Echo IgG(+) and Echo IgM(+) ($p=0.0000$ and 0.0455 respectively).

Gender

The samples tested for Coxsackie came from 2921 males and 2447 females, while the samples tested for Echo belonged to 737 males and 549 females.

Coxsackie: Out of the 5368 examined samples, 653 were IgM positive, 296 (45.3%) belonging to males and 357 (54.7%) to females, while 2234 were IgG positive, 1186 (53.1%) from males and 1048 (46.9%) from females (Table 2). Coxsackie viruses were found to be common among the population; regarding specific immunity, prevalence of males was noted ($p=0.0000$), while higher incidence rates were found in females ($p=0.0007$). Regarding the number of tested samples per gender, the predominance of females IgM(+) was statistically important ($p=0.0000$).

Echo: IgM specific antibodies were detected in 98 samples (males 52/98, 53.1%; females 46/98, 46.9%) and IgG in 189 samples (males 106/189, 56.1%; females 83/189, 43.9%) (Table 2). Statistically, males were not infected by Echo virus more than females ($p=0.3914$) but presented higher rate of immunity ($p=0.0180$), which might be due to the difference in the number of tested samples between males and females (IgG positive males 106 and IgG positive females 83). The immunity rate was indicated by IgG positives 189/1286 (14.7%) while the incidence by IgM positives was 98/1286 (7.6%).

Season

Outbreaks of Coxsackie peaked in spring (34.6%). The comparison with summer, autumn and winter resulted to a statistically significant increase ($p=0.0000$, 0.0003 and 0.0000 respectively). For Echo viruses the total spring-summer positives were compared with the autumn-winter ones, since the numbers of positives of each season-pair were numerically similar, and bigger numbers of positive samples were detected in the autumn-winter period ($p=0.0006$). A similar com-

parison revealed no statistically significant difference for Coxsackie positives ($p=0.1665$). (Figure 3)

Clinical syndromes

The tested samples came from patients presenting a large variety of clinical manifestations. The percentages of the clinical syndromes derived from the total number of the IgM positive patients (Coxsackie 653, Echo 98). Most of the IgM positive patients presented more than one symptoms due to the infection. (Table 3, Figure 4)

In the IgM(+) Coxsackie patients, the most common clinical syndrome was nonspecific respiratory tract infection; a statistically significant difference resulted from the estimated $p<0,05$ in comparison with each one of all the other clinical groups. Comparing to the clinical group with the largest number of cases (lymphadenitis-splenohepatomegaly) $p=0.0197$, while comparing to the group with the least cases (aseptic meningitis) $p=0.0000$. On the other hand, in the IgM(+) Echo group the most common clinical syndrome was acute gastroenteritis, though statistically significant increase was found when compared only to some of the clinical groups, such as the group of myo-pericarditis ($p=0.0013$), arthritis-myositis ($p=0.0071$), aseptic meningitis ($p=0.0143$) and cutaneous rash ($p=0.0143$).

The Coxsackie IgM(+) group was further examined, because of the statistically significant difference observed between the two genders (females' prevalence, $p=0.0000$). Genders were compared for each clinical syndrome. (Table 4, Figure 5)

For females IgM(+), it was observed that group 2 (respiratory tract infections) and group 6 (aseptic meningitis) showed the highest and lowest rates (20.4% and 3.6%) respectively, than all the other groups when compared statistically (indicatively, for groups 2-1 and 2-6 $p=0.0226$ and 0.0000 respectively while for groups 6-4 and 6-5 $p=0.0454$). As for males IgM(+), group 2 (respiratory tract infections) was also dominant, when compared with the other clinical syndromes (p varied from 0.0000 to 0.0465). Thus, statistically significant difference lacked only in comparison with group 8 (lymphadenitis, splenohepatomegaly) ($p=0.3364$), which though is not evaluable, due to the fact that both these clinical syndromes could coexist in most infections. Groups 5 (arthritis, myositis) and 6 (aseptic meningitis) with the lowest number of cases are statistically different from group 3 (acute gastroenteritis) ($p=0.0421$), group 1 (nonspecific febrile illness) ($p=0.0040$), group 8 (lymphadenitis, splenohepatomegaly) ($p=0.0001$) and group 2 (respiratory tract infections) ($p=0.0000$), but not with groups 7 (cutaneous rash) ($p=0.6272$), 10 (other) ($p=0.1712$) and 9 (haematological disorders) ($p=0.569$).

Table 3

Distribution of clinical syndromes for the total number of tested samples for Coxsackie and Echo viruses, as well as for IgM(+) samples

	Clinical Syndromes	Coxsackie	Echo	Coxsackie IgM (+)	Echo IgM (+)
Group 1	Nonspecific febrile illness	758 (14,1%)	204 (15,9%)	90 (13,8%)	13 (13,3%)
Group 2	Respiratory tract infections	954 (17,8%)	153 (11,9%)	130(19,9%)	12 (12,2%)
Group 3	Acute gastroenteritis	532 (9,9%)	165 (12,8%)	61 (9,3%)	20 (20,4%)
Group 4	Myo-pericarditis	700 (13,0%)	216 (16,8%)	47 (7,2%)	5 (5,1%)
Group 5	Arthritis, myositis	303 (5,6%)	105 (8,2%)	44 (6,7%)	7 (7,1%)
Group 6	Aseptic meningitis	332 (6,2%)	94 (7,3%)	31 (4,7%)	8 (8,2%)
Group 7	Cutaneous rash	295 (5,5%)	79 (6,1%)	48 (7,4%)	8 (8,2%)
Group 8	Lymphadenitis, splenohepatomegaly	437 (8,1%)	86 (6,7%)	98 (15,0%)	14 (14,3%)
Group 9	Haematological manifestations	585 (10,9%)	104 (8,1%)	81 (12,4%)	14 (14,3%)
Group 10	Others	879 (16,4%)	204 (15,9%)	64 (9,8%)	16 (16,3%)
Total		5368	1286	694	117

Figure 4 Distribution of clinical syndromes for IgM(+) Coxsackie and IgM(+) Echo virus (IgM(+) Coxsackie N=653, IgM(+) Echo N=98)

Table 4 Distribution of clinical syndromes for Coxsackie male and female IgM(+)

	Clinical Syndromes	Males IgM(+)	Females IgM(+)	P
Group 1	Nonspecific febrile illness	40 (13,5%)	50 (14,0%)	0.8559
Group 2	Respiratory tract infections	58 (19,6%)	73 (20,4%)	0.7863
Group 3	Acute gastroenteritis	33 (11,1%)	28 (7,8%)	0.1485
Group 4	Myo-pericarditis	22 (7,4%)	25 (7,0%)	0.8325
Group 5	Arthritis, myositis	19 (6,4%)	25 (7,0%)	0.7670
Group 6	Aseptic meningitis	19 (6,4%)	13 (3,6%)	0.1017
Group 7	Cutaneous rash	22 (7,4%)	26 (7,3%)	0.9419
Group 8	Lymphadenitis, splenohepatomegaly	49 (16,6%)	49 (13,7%)	0.3137
Group 9	Haematological manifestations	32 (10,8%)	47 (13,2%)	0.3584
Group 10	Others	28 (9,5%)	36 (10,1%)	0.7893

Figure 5

Distribution of clinical syndromes for Coxsackie male and female IgM(+). Fe = nonspecific febrile illness; Re = respiratory tract infections; Ga = gastroenteritis; AM = arthritis, myositis; Me = aseptic meningitis; Ca = myo-pericarditis; Ra = cutaneous rash; LS = lymphadenitis, splenohepatomegaly; Ha = haematological manifestations; O = others

Comparing males and females for group 2 (respiratory tract infections), no statistical difference between genders and clinical syndromes was proved to exist ($p=0.7863$).

Discussion

The worldwide prevalence of the most important enteroviral infection, poliomyelitis, has remarkably decreased due to the enhanced vaccination. However, non-polio enteroviral infections are still a major cause for a variety of clinical syndromes globally.^{25,26} Therefore, periodical studies greatly contribute to the surveillance of enteroviruses globally.

In Europe, studies suggest that non-polio enteroviruses infect mainly young children (age 1-6 years) and present the highest rates of mortality and morbidity in this age group, furthermore as age increases the prevalence decreases.^{22,21} The present study results to the same conclusion, that the prevalence in the age group 1-6 is the most common. However, surprisingly there has been a significantly high prevalence of the Echovirus in the adults, age group 19-60, suggesting an unusual viral circulation at the period. No similar report was found in other studies. In accordance to the pattern of widely spread infectious diseases, the present study indicates that Coxsackie virus incidence increases on children and especially young children; this is statistically confirmed not only for acute and recent infections but also for previous, immunizing ones. However, notably the immunity to Coxsackie viruses shows a downward trend as age increases, thus suggesting that specific immunity may be relatively temporary.

In the present study provides information on a significant number of the examined samples indicated currently or previously infected individuals. Interestingly, a statistically important female predominance among the Coxsackie IgM positives was found although no difference between genders has been reported by other similar studies, as the ones conducted in China,²⁷ Taipei,²⁸ UK,²⁹ while a broad epidemiological

research in the USA reveals male predominance only <20 years of age.³⁰

Though studies indicate that in temperate climates enteroviral infections peak during summer or/and autumn,^{25,26,21,29} Echo infections in the studied area presented a rather different seasonal distribution, i.e. positive samples "moved" a little later (autumn-winter) in the year. Unlikely, Coxsackie infections presented an impressive peak particularly in spring.

Coxsackie and Echo viruses have been detected in patients with a variety of clinical syndromes, such as sporadic acute gastroenteritis, lymphadenitis, splenohepatomegaly, aseptic meningitis, encephalitis, myopericarditis, cutaneous rash (hand, foot and mouth disease), nonspecific respiratory tract infections, nonspecific febrile illness, as also indicated by many researchers in recent and earlier studies.^{4,5,9,13,12,15,18,6} Even though the variety of the clinical syndromes caused by Coxsackie and Echo viruses was expected, differences in the frequency of the syndromes were noted, while combinations of clinical manifestations appeared as well. Though respiratory infections are often caused by various Coxsackie viruses, as noted during the recent decades,^{31,32,33} the present study suggests that respiratory illness was the main clinical result of Coxsackie infections. Interestingly Greece has experienced an unusual circulation of cardiotropic Coxsackie strains in 2002, which was at first wrongly thought to be a real outbreak.³⁴ On the other hand, though Echoviruses are most commonly associated with aseptic meningitis and acute gastroenteritis as confirmed by various studies worldwide,^{35,36,37} the present study failed to confirm these facts since the variety of comparisons among clinical presentations of Echo infections provided no safe conclusions.

In conclusion, the epidemiological approach of non-polio enteroviruses in N. Greece has revealed similarities to global findings but slight differences as well. Aiming to a complete and lasting study of non-polio enteroviruses, continuous monitoring would be necessary.

Περίληψη

Επιδημιολογικά στοιχεία για τους ιούς Coxsackie και Echo στη Β. Ελλάδα

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Ερευνάται η κυκλοφορία των Coxsackie και Echo σε μία περίοδο 14 ετών στη Β. Ελλάδα. Καταγράφηκαν κλινικά δεδομένα και ανιχνεύθηκαν ειδικά IgM και IgG αντισώματα για 6.654 δείγματα ορού αίματος (5.368 για Coxsackie, 1.286 για Echo). Τα δείγματα συνελέγησαν από νοσοκομεία της Β. Ελλάδος και για τον ορολογικό έλεγχο χρησιμοποιήθηκαν τεχνικές ELISA και IFA. Τα αποτελέσματα απέδωσαν 653 IgM θετικά και 2.234 IgG θετικά δείγματα για ιούς Coxsackie καθώς και 98 IgM θετικά και 189 IgG θετικά δείγματα για ιούς Echo. Λοιμώξεις από ιούς Coxsackie και Echo παρουσίασαν και τα δύο φύλλα, παρατηρήθηκε όμως στατιστικά σημαντική υπεροχή των IgM αντισωμάτων έναντι Coxsackie στα θήλεα άτομα. 34,6% των λοιμώξεων από Coxsackie σημειώθηκαν άνοιξη, ενώ οι λοιμώξεις από Echo συνέβησαν κυρίως φθινόπωρο και χειμώνα (62,2%). Ο αριθμός των λοιμώξεων γενικά βρέθηκε να μειώνεται με την πρόοδο της ηλικίας, εκτός των λοιμώξεων από Echo που έπληξαν τα άτομα 19-60 ετών περισσότερο από τα παιδιά 0-6 ετών. Οι ιοί Coxsackie συχνότερα προκάλεσαν αναπνευστικά νοσήματα (IgM 19,9%) με στατιστικά σημαντική διαφορά από τις υπόλοιπες κλινικές εκδηλώσεις, ενώ οι Echo κυρίως προκάλεσαν γαστρεντερίτιδα (20,4%) αν και δίχως συνολική στατιστικά σημαντική διαφορά. Δεν εμφανίστηκε στατιστικά σημαντική διαφορά στις κλινικές εκδηλώσεις ανάμεσα στα δύο φύλλα.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Coxsackie, ECHO, εντεροϊοί, Β. Ελλάδα, επιδημιολογία

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